

Chewed torcs from Snettisham?

By Tess Machling

A friend (thank you David!) today reminded me of something I've been intending to write about for quite a long time, but never quite got round to. As it's Christmas and everyone is in need of light entertainment, I thought it might be time.

The long and the short of it is that, for three pieces of torc from Snettisham, it looks like an Iron Age person gave them a bit of a chew! Yes, really! But approaching this subject is not easy. It's a bit of a toothy topic that really needs drilling into, so I'll stop filling time and get on with it... [stop groaning at the back!].

A strange bit of evidence

Back in April 2021, I was looking for something else (these things always involve 'looking for something else'...) when I noticed some strange marks on one of the pieces of torc from Hoard F at Snettisham. Torc F63 (British Museum accession number [1991,0501.33](#)), a piece of dorsal muff from a tubular torc, jumped out at me (Fig. 1). I couldn't help but think that the torc had been bitten, but that was a crazy idea, wasn't it?

Figure 1: Torc F63, with what look like bite marks on the bottom of the torc piece. (Image © The Trustees of the British Museum)

I then looked for other photos of this torc and, on the other side of the edge from the tooth marks, there were yet more marks that could not be easily explained as tooling marks (Fig. 2)

2: the odd marks on the reverse of Torc F63. (Image © The Trustees of the British Museum)

From both sides it really did look like someone had bitten down hard on the edge (Fig. 3) of this torc:

Figure 3: The possible biting of the edge of Torc F63. (Image © The Trustees of the British Museum)

Honestly, I still didn't believe that this could be so, but it was amusing so I thought I'd check if there were any more torcs from Snettisham that could have been munched and...

... sure enough, there were more, two more (Fig. 4) to be precise: Torcs F52 (British Museum accession number [1991,0501.76](#)) and F53 (British Museum accession number [1991,0501.118](#)) both of which looked like they'd been given a hefty chomp!

Figure 4: Torcs F52 (left) & F53 (right). (Image © The Trustees of the British Museum)

Torc F52 in particular made me chuckle. It reminded me of that thing that I - and I suspect a lot of us - do of absent mindedly folding and then biting flat a bit of tin foil, or cake wrapper (try it with a foil mince-pie case folks... it's very satisfying!).

Torc F53 looked like it had been bitten to seal the end of the tube, which had contained five gold coins (Fig. 5) when originally found [...and yes, I did nearly sing 'five go-old rings' then...].

Figure 5: Torc F53, with the coins supposed to have been found within it. (Image © The Trustees of the British Museum)

And there we left it.

In September 2022, I happened to be in the British Museum looking at some other gold (oh, its a hard life) and was able to get Torc F63 off display and have a look at it under a microscope (Fig. 8).

Figure 8: Torc F63 under a microscope (Image © The Trustees of the British Museum)

There was nothing in what I saw that disproved the biting theory: these just did not look like 'tool' marks. 'Tooth' marks however? Maybe??

So what does this all mean? To be honest I have no idea! Were they carrying out some bizarre biting ritual on torcs? Were they checking if something was really gold? Or were they - if these really are bite marks - just doing that very human thing of doing something just because they could? Perhaps the absent minded action of an Iron Age person 2000 or so years ago?

More work will be needed to tell if these pieces really were bitten, but they are certainly different to anything I've seen before on torcs, and only appear on these few examples from Snettisham. I would love it if they really were bitten. What do you think?

As ever, it's good to torc!